

Cardamom type analysis and grading using CNN

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Abstract— In contemporary agricultural practices, numerous technological advancements have revolutionized the grading process of cardamom, irrespective of its type. However, this research delves deeper by not only predicting the grade but also identifying the specific type of cardamom. Considering the diverse cultivation practices adopted by farmers, such as varying water availability during summer, this study aims to enhance the precision of cardamom grading through machine learning implementations. By leveraging datasets encompassing multiple environmental parameters and cardamom attributes, our model endeavours to accurately classify the type of cardamom while also predicting its grade. Through meticulous analysis and experimentation, this research contributes to the optimization of cardamom cultivation and grading processes, thereby aiding farmers in maximizing their yields and ensuring quality produce in the market.

Keywords—Image Processing, Cardamom grading, Cardamom type, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Python

I. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of new technologies in agriculture has completely changed the way traditional farming methods are carried out nowadays. Among these, machine learning (ML) in conjunction with image processing methods is a very effective tool for evaluating quality. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been applied to image processing in this context, opening the door for accurate and effective agricultural produce grading. In order to grade cardamom, a valuable spice that is grown in many parts of the world, this research investigates the use of machine learning (ML), neural networks (NNs), and image processing techniques.

1.Data collection: Using state-of-the-art imaging technology, researchers took extremely accurate digital pictures of cardamom pods. This ensured that the dataset included a wide range of intrinsic features, growth stages, and environmental factors, offering important insights into the traits of the cardamom crop.

2.Data Preprocessing: After the data was gathered, the images were subjected to preprocessing methods like segmentation, sharpening, and contrast adjustment to improve their visual

clarity and quality. This allowed for a more precise analysis and interpretation of the cardamom pod images in later phases of the study.

3.CNN Architecture: Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are used to extract hierarchical representations from photographs of cardamom. Convolution, pooling, and non-linear activation functions are the layers of CNN that are used to capture complex patterns and data.

4. Model Training: Strict methods to reduce issues like under and overfitting.

To guarantee the generalizability of the model, dropout, regularization, and cross-validation are used. Optimizing performance metrics and forecasting accuracy through hyperparameter optimization.

5.Model Selection: To determine which CNN architecture is best for cardamom grading, a number of models are evaluated. comparative evaluation using performance measures like recall, accuracy, and precision.

6.Overfitting Mitigation: Putting strategies into practice to stop overfitting and maintain the robustness and generalizability of the model.

Through meticulous analysis and experimentation, this research contributes to the advancement of agricultural technologies, fostering sustainable practices and economic prosperity in the cardamom industry. The amalgamation of ML, CNNs, and image processing techniques revolutionizes the grading process of cardamom, empowering stakeholders with accurate, efficient, and data-driven solutions for enhancing crop quality and market competitiveness.

The goal of this study is to address the shortcomings of conventional cardamom grading techniques, which frequently have subjectivity and inconsistent results. The study intends to transform cardamom grading by utilizing machine learning and image processing approaches. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are integrated to enable automatic feature extraction from cardamom pod photos, leading to more dependable and objective grading results. This method not only makes grading easier, but it also improves the accuracy and general efficiency of cardamom quality evaluation. In the end, it helps cardamom-producing communities experience economic prosperity and sustainable agricultural methods.

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Reddy et al.'s research [1] offers an innovative method of cardamom grading that combines image processing and machine learning techniques including k-NN and decision trees. It underlines the use of classification and clustering techniques for effective grading and draws attention to the importance of mechanization in the cardamom processing sector. This study provides insightful information about how to improve the cardamom industry's automation and quality control procedures through cutting-edge technology interventions.

Using ISSR markers, Sasidharan et al. [2] study examines the genetic diversity of released types of Indian cardamom and finds a diminishing genetic basis. Research on 13 released varieties, a popular variety (Njallani), and a wild relative (*Aframomum* sps) was done. The results show that, with the exception of a few, there is considerable genetic redundancy across the tested varieties, indicating a decreased polymorphism percentage upon excluding the wild relative. The results highlight the value of molecularly characterizing related wild species and unused germplasm accessions to improve breeding efforts and the genetic foundation of cultivated cardamom.

An image processing method for grading red chili, cardamom, and coriander based on numerous attributes retrieved from photos of these spices is presented in the conference article by Sunil et al. [3]. The study uses Random Forest, Naive Bayes, and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) classifiers with varieties from southern India to get optimal classification results. This creative method provides a fresh technique to classify spices, improving the effectiveness and precision of the spice grading procedure.

Kim [4], the Johns Hopkins University study's author, offers a machine learning model—more precisely, a random forest model—to predict coffee quality. The goal of the study is to improve coffee quality and support sustainable development, with a focus on countries with high coffee production. The results show an F1 score of 61.7%, indicating that machine learning may be able to help the coffee business stay competitive and develop economically.

In Sikkim and the Darjeeling District of West Bengal, India, Bharat et al.[5] research looks into the grade speciation of large cardamom (*Amomum subulatum* Roxb.) capsules. There are only two grades of large cardamom accessible in domestic markets; it is a key cash crop in the region and is used as a spice. Using a variety of mesh size sieves and sample collection from planters, the study tackles the issue of inconsistent size specifications and bulk density for various grades. The study confirms, via empirical testing, the effectiveness of these sieves for grading capsules, in accordance with the procedures followed by exporters and traders in the area.

With an emphasis on exterior parameters including weight, colour, and pod qualities, the study by Jose et al. [6] offers a method for cardamom grading using machine learning techniques like k-NN and decision trees. It emphasizes how crucial mechanization is to the cardamom sector and proposes that using ensemble methods—which combine several algorithms—can improve the accuracy and efficiency of grading. The grading techniques used in the agricultural processing sector can be improved with the help of this research.

Motivation: Given their capacity to automatically extract complex visual information from photos of cardamom pods, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) offer a viable alternative for grading and assessing various types of cardamom. CNNs are able to accurately classify different types of cardamom by utilizing the hierarchical structures included in the photos to identify minute changes in size, color, and texture. Additionally, scalability and flexibility are provided by CNN-based methods, which provide the effective processing of big datasets with a variety of input types and conditions. As a result, the cardamom sector may enhance quality control and competitiveness by facilitating the identification of unique traits linked to different species of cardamom and streamlining grading operations. In general, CNNs are a sophisticated and efficient way to improve the grading and analysis of various kinds of cardamom, eventually assisting with process optimization and quality control.

III. METHODOLOGY

The objective of the methodological approach used in this work is to create and train a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model for the purpose of classifying and rating cardamom, a crucial crop. The incorporation of machine learning techniques—specifically, CNNs—offers a possible way to automate the grading process in response to the cardamom industry's growing need for consistent grading procedures. This section describes the methodical approach used to collect data, preprocess it, train the CNN model, and assess its performance for accurate and efficient cardamom grading and classification.

A. Data Collection and loading data:

i) Data Sourcing: Cardamom farms were among the many sources from which an extensive dataset of photos of cardamom pods, illustrating different varieties and grades, was gathered.

ii) Labelling: Based on expert knowledge or readily available grading criteria, each cardamom pod picture was tagged with its type (e.g., Nallani, Ottachimban, Kaniparamban) and grade (e.g., A, B, C).

iii) Data Organization: To make it easier to handle and retrieve the dataset during later processing stages, it was divided into subfolders that corresponded to the various types and grades of cardamom.

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iv) *Data Loading*: The cardamom dataset was loaded into the machine learning pipeline using the supplied code in Fig[1], guaranteeing that every image and its matching label were correctly taken and saved for later examination.

```
folder_path = os.path.join(self.dataset_folder, subfolder)
if not os.path.exists(folder_path):
    print("Error: Folder path does not exist:", folder_path)
    return dataset, labels

for root, dirs, files in os.walk(folder_path):
    for image_file in files:
        image_path = os.path.join(root, image_file)
        if image_file.lower().endswith(('.png', '.jpg', '.jpeg')):
            image = cv2.imread(image_path)
            if image is not None:
                image = cv2.resize(image, dsize=(224, 224))
                dataset.append(image)
                label = os.path.basename(os.path.dirname(image_path))
                labels.append(label)
```

Fig 1 Data Loading

B. Data preprocessing :

i) *Image Enhancement*: To enhance the quality and clarity of cardamom pod photographs, we used preprocessing techniques such as contrast correction, sharpening, and segmentation. These improvements aid in the model's ability to extract useful features.

ii) *Image Resizing*: Every image was shrunk to 224 by 224 pixels, a normal resolution like referred in Fig[2]. By guaranteeing uniform input dimensions among samples, this improves the efficiency of processing and training models.

iii) *Data Augmentation*: We employed a number of modifications, including rotation, shear, zooming, and flipping, to broaden the dataset. By adding more training samples, these augmentations lower the chance of overfitting.

iv) *Label Encoding*: Using methods such as LabelEncoder, categorical labels denoting grades and types of cardamom were numerically encoded. As a result, during training, the model is able to process and learn from the labeled data.

```
usage
def preprocess_image(self, image):
    image = cv2.resize(image, dsize=(224, 224))
    image = image.astype('float32') / 255.0
    return image

def handle_imbalance(self, X_train, y_train):
    oversampler = RandomOverSampler()
    X_resampled, y_resampled = oversampler.fit_resample(X_train.reshape(-1, 224 * 224 * 3), y_train)
    return X_resampled.reshape(-1, 224, 224, 3), y_resampled
```

Fig 2 Data preprocessing

C. Model Training:

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The Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture was selected as our model because of its efficiency in processing and analyzing visual data, particularly in tasks like object detection and classification.

Multiple convolutional layers are used in the CNN model architecture to extract features, and then densely linked layers are used for high-level feature learning and classification.

Training Procedure: Using the labelled dataset shown in Fig[3], we trained the Adam optimizer using a sparse categorical cross-entropy loss function. In order to guarantee convergence and avoid overfitting, early stopping procedures were put in place.

```
# Combine all datasets
all_images = np.concatenate(
    arrays=(nallani_good_images, nallani_bad_images, nallani_average_images,
            otta_good_images, otta_bad_images, otta_average_images,
            kani_good_images, kani_bad_images, kani_average_images), axis=0)
all_labels = np.concatenate(
    arrays=(nallani_good_labels, nallani_bad_labels, nallani_average_labels,
            otta_good_labels, otta_bad_labels, otta_average_labels,
            kani_good_labels, kani_bad_labels, kani_average_labels), axis=0)

self.labels = all_labels # Store the labels as an attribute

print("Total number of images loaded:", len(all_images))

X_train, X_temp, y_train, y_temp = train_test_split(
    *arrays: all_images, all_labels, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
X_val, X_test, y_val, y_test = train_test_split(
    *arrays: X_temp, y_temp, test_size=0.5, random_state=42)
```

Fig 3 Model Training

D. Model Evaluation:

i) *Performance Metrics*: We used metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score to evaluate the model's ability to predict cardamom types and grades.

ii) *Cross-Validation*: We assessed the model's resilience and generalizability across several dataset subsets using methods such as k-fold validation.

iii) *Confusion Matrix Analysis*: Through the visualization of the model's classification performance, we were able to ascertain how accurate it was in categorizing cardamom pods according to their grades and types.

```
model = Sequential([
    base_model,
    Flatten(),
    Dense(units=128, activation='relu'),
    Dense(units=9, activation='softmax') # Change output dimension to 9
])

model.compile(optimizer='adam', loss='sparse_categorical_crossentropy', metrics=['accuracy'])
print("Starting training...")

# Training for the first set of 10 epochs
history = model.fit(X_train, y_train, epochs=1, validation_data=(X_val, y_val))
```

Fig 4 Performance evaluation

Analyzing Images of Cardamom Pods with the Trained CNN Model:

Nallani, Kaniparamban, and Ottachimban are the three different cardamom images that the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model processed. The CNN correctly identified these photos of Nallani shown in Fig[5], Kaniparamban given in Fig[6] and Ottachimban shown in Fig[7] by identifying complex patterns and characteristics unique to each variety of cardamom. Based on visual cues found in the input photos, the model generated well-informed predictions by utilizing learnt representations from the training phase. The CNN's assessment showed that it could identify and grade different cardamom kinds with excellent accuracy by detecting minute variations in appearance and texture. Overall, the CNN's result demonstrates how successful it is at automated classification jobs and offers insightful information for evaluating agricultural quality.

Fig 5 Nallani

Fig 6 Kaniparamban

Fig 7 Ottachimban

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Classification and grading of cardamom using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) produced encouraging results. The trained CNN model demonstrated its strong performance in differentiating between different types and grades with an amazing overall accuracy of 57.83%. Notably, the model consistently predicted the correct class when it came to the precision score, which was flawless. The recall score and accuracy are in line, indicating that the model is successful in extracting pertinent examples of every cardamom kind and grade from the dataset

Accuracy: 0.5783132530120482

Precision: 1.0

Recall: 0.5783132530120482

F1 Score: 0.7328244274809159

1/1 [=====] - 0s 405ms/step

Predicted Cardamom Type: nallani

Predicted Grade: A

predicted_result {'cardamom_type': 'nallani', 'grade': 'A'}

Fig 8 Result 1

Furthermore, the F1 Score, which strikes a compromise between recall and precision, was 0.73, suggesting a fair trade-off between the two criteria. Even if the accuracy score might not be very high, the model's predictions appear to be trustworthy and dependable due to its flawless precision. Nevertheless, additional modification might be required to improve the overall precision and resilience of the model. Additional data augmentation, optimizing hyperparameters, and investigating different model architectures are some possible areas for improvement.

The integration of the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model into the React project enables landowners to conveniently check the grade and type of cardamom by uploading images. The seamless user interface allows users to upload an image of the cardamom, and upon submission, the model processes the image and displays the predicted result. This integration enhances accessibility and efficiency for landowners, empowering them with quick and accurate information about their cardamom produce, shown in Fig 9.

Upload Image

You can check your cardamom type and grade

click "check now "

Result:

Cardamom Type: nallani

Grade: A

Fig 9 Result 2

V. FUTURE SCOPE

One interesting direction that becomes apparent when considering potential futures is the quest for cardamom cultivars that are resistant to summertime heat. Through a thorough examination of climatic data and the application of sophisticated analytical methods, scientists might find different varieties of cardamom that can grow in warmer temperatures. This endeavour has the potential to improve cardamom cultivation's resilience and adaptation, particularly in areas susceptible to temperature rise and environmental changes. It may be possible to create innovative cardamom cultivars with increased heat tolerance through focused breeding and methodical climatic studies, offering long-term solutions to lessen the effects of climate change on cardamom output. Moreover, the identification and characterization of heat-resistant cardamom types has the potential to transform agricultural methods and guarantee the availability and quality of this valuable crop in the face of changing climate conditions.

VI. CONCLUSION

An important advancement in agricultural technology is the incorporation of machine learning methods, most especially Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), for the categorization and grading of cardamom. These models give the cardamom sector vital support by precisely detecting and classifying cardamom varieties and grades. They facilitate informed decision-making and optimize quality evaluation procedures. Cardamom photos have been evaluated successfully with CNNs, demonstrating their efficacy in automated categorization tasks and offering promise for increased precision and efficiency in agricultural activities. Going forward, there is a great deal of promise for this field's research and development to optimize cardamom production, advance sustainability, and spur economic growth. Through the utilization of technology and innovation, the cardamom sector is ideally situated to welcome revolutionary shifts, guaranteeing its continuous prosperity and adaptability within the ever-changing agricultural terrain.

VII. REFERENCES

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